

High Resolution Evapotranspiration Map Over Austria: Leveraging AI and Sentinel-2

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Abstract

This paper presents a deep learning pipeline for high-resolution evapotranspiration (ET) estimation over Austria using Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery and a digital elevation model as inputs, and spatially-sharpened ECOSTRESS measurements as the training reference. The model, a ResNet18-based U-Net architecture pre-trained on Sentinel-2 data, produces daily ET maps at 10-metre resolution, bridging the gap between the 70-metre ECOSTRESS footprint and the spatial detail required for urban and agricultural applications. A validation study is presented at the AKH Vienna site, comparing model outputs against raw ECOSTRESS acquisitions and field lysimeter measurements. Results confirm that the model accurately reproduces its training target, achieving consistent agreement with ECOSTRESS across 2022–2024. Comparison with ground-truth lysimeter data reveals a systematic positive bias, identified as partially inherited from the ECOSTRESS training signal itself. The implications for training data selection, model improvement, and broader validation strategies are discussed.

1. Introduction

Climate change is accelerating at an unprecedented rate, with Austria recording mean temperature increases at more than twice the global average (IEA, 2024). Urban areas, agricultural landscapes, and mountain ecosystems are all experiencing significant impacts, making climate adaptation monitoring a critical operational priority. Evapotranspiration (ET) is a central variable in the water and energy cycles, linking vegetation health, soil moisture, and atmospheric dynamics. Its accurate estimation at high spatial resolution is essential for informing **green infrastructure planning**, **urban heat island** assessment and **irrigation management**.

Satellite-based ET estimation typically relies on thermal infrared measurements. The ECOSTRESS instrument aboard the International Space Station provides daily ET maps at 70-metre resolution globally, offering a valuable observational record. However, this resolution is insufficient to resolve fine-scale urban features such as green roofs, street-level vegetation, or

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individual agricultural parcels. Sentinel-2, with its 10–20 meter multispectral bands and 5-day revisit time, provides complementary high-resolution spectral observations but lacks direct thermal ET measurement.

This work presents a methodology that uses Sentinel-2 and a digital elevation model as inputs to a deep learning model trained on sharpened ECOSTRESS data (10m resolution), producing ET maps at 10m resolution. The service has been developed in the context of the FFG project GET-ET and is operationally deployed for monthly Austria-wide mapping on the GTIF platform. This paper extends the original methodology description with validation study conducted at the AKH Vienna monitoring site, analysing model performance against both the raw ECOSTRESS training signal and independent field lysimeter measurements on the AKH Vienna green roof.

2. Methodology

2.1. Training Data Preparation

ECOSTRESS ECO_L3T_JET.002 daily ET granules were selected as the training reference (Hook et al., 2023), providing 70-metre resolution ET estimates in mm/day. To align the reference with the 10-metre Sentinel-2 input grid, ECOSTRESS imagery was spatially sharpened using a Python implementation of the Data Mining Sharpener (PyDMS) (Gao et al.,2012). The sharpening uses Leaf Area Index (LAI) values derived from Sentinel-2 (produced using Snappy tools) to guide the spatial disaggregation, producing 10-metre ET fields that follow the structural patterns of the input imagery.

Sentinel-2 Level-2A products were used as model inputs, comprising ten spectral bands at 10 and 20-metre resolution (resampled to 10 metres), supplemented by a digital elevation model from the Copernicus programme. Scene-level masking was applied using the Scene Classification Layer (SCL), retaining pixels classified as vegetation (class 4) or bare soil (class 5). A dataset of 140 paired Sentinel-2 / ECOSTRESS acquisitions was assembled over Austria between 2019 and 2025, accounting for the temporal correlation and atmospheric conditions of both sensors.

2.2. Model Architecture

The estimation model is a U-Net (Ronneberger et al.,2015) with a ResNet18 encoder, pre-trained on Sentinel-2 imagery. The encoder extracts multi-scale spatial features at four resolution levels (H/4 through H/32), which are progressively upsampled through a decoder with bilinear interpolation and skip connections to recover full 10-metre resolution. The network receives 11 input channels (10 spectral bands + DEM) and produces a single-channel ET map.

Training employed a perceptual loss function combining pixel-level ET accuracy with structural similarity to the Sentinel-2 input, encouraging the model to produce outputs that maintain the high-frequency spatial structure of the input imagery. The model achieved a Structural Similarity

Index Measure (SSIM) of 0.91 on the training dataset, indicating strong fidelity to the reference data.

2.3. Inference and Operational Deployment

Inference is applied via a sliding-window tiling strategy with overlapping patches to minimise boundary artefacts. Predicted patches are assembled into a full-scene ET map. The pipeline is containerised in Docker with GPU support (CUDA 11.8), producing Cloud-Optimised GeoTIFF (COG) mosaics over Austria in EPSG:3857 at 10-metre resolution, published through the GTIF platform.

3. Validation Study

3.1. Study Site and Data

Validation was conducted at the AKH Vienna monitoring site (lat: 48.2212°N, lon: 16.3428°E), an urban green roof instrumented with a ground-truth ET measurement systems. Ground-truth data span June 2022 to December 2023.

Model predictions were extracted at the site coordinate from inference outputs produced over the period June 2022 to December 2024, yielding 94 valid acquisition dates. ECOSTRESS ECO_L3T_JET.002 pixel values were extracted at the same location for the full study period using the 33UWP MGRS tile, resulting in 108 valid daily acquisitions.

3.2. Model vs ECOSTRESS

The first validation axis assesses whether the model accurately learns to reproduce its training target. Model outputs and ECOSTRESS values were compared on matching acquisition dates. Figure 1 shows a representative acquisition over Vienna, illustrating the spatial detail achieved at 10m resolution compared to the 70m ECOSTRESS data. Figure 2 presents the temporal evolution of both signals across the full 2022–2024 period.

Figure 1 : Comparison between model output (left) and raw ecostress data (right) over Vienna, Austria

Results show strong agreement in both magnitude and seasonal dynamics. Both signals capture the expected seasonal cycle, with ET peaks in summer (June–August) reaching 3–4 mm/day and low values in winter below 0.5 mm/day. The model closely tracks ECOSTRESS values across inter-annual variability, with no systematic divergence over time. This confirms that the end-to-end pipeline — from Sentinel-2 input through the trained U-Net to the reconstructed ET map — successfully generalises the ECOSTRESS signal to 10-metre resolution.

Figure 2 : GET-ET Model Output vs ECOSTRESS ECO_L3T_JET over AKH Vienna Site (2022–2024)

3.3. Model vs Ground Truth

Point-scale validation was performed by comparing model predictions against the AKH lysimeter measurements on dates where both were available, yielding 44 paired observations across June 2022 – December 2023.

Comparison	RMSE (mm/day)	Bias (mm/day)	R ²
[A] Model vs Ground Truth	1.43	+0.748	0.032
[B] Model vs ECOSTRESS	0.121	-0.076	0.987

Table 1 : Validation Statistics of the GET-ET Evapotranspiration Model at the AKH Vienna Monitoring Site

The model shows a systematic positive bias of +0.748 mm/day against the GT, with low temporal correlation (R²=0.032). Despite this, the temporal envelope analysis (Figure 2) reveals that the model broadly captures the seasonal ET range, summer peaks of 2.5–3 mm/day are generally reproduced, but does not track the rapid ET drawdown events observed in the field measurements, particularly the sharp decline from summer peaks into autumn. The model transitions more gradually, consistent with a training signal (ECOSTRESS) that averages ET over a 70-metre landscape footprint rather than the specific green roof substrate.

Figure 3 : GET-ET Model Output vs Ground Truth Measurements AKH Vienna Site (2022–2023)

The [B] comparison confirms that on the 8 dates where both model output and ECOSTRESS acquisition coincide (having valid data on the pixel of interest), the model reproduces its training target with high fidelity ($R^2=0.987$, $RMSE=0.121$ mm/day). The near-zero bias of -0.076 mm/day indicates no systematic offset between the model and ECOSTRESS. This confirms the model is functioning correctly, the gap observed in [A] is therefore attributable to the mismatch between the ECOSTRESS training signal and the GT measurement, rather than to a failure of the model to learn its target.

4. Discussion

4.1. Training Signal Quality

The validation results highlight that the principal limitation of the current model is not architectural but stems from the choice of training reference. ECOSTRESS measures ET over a 70-metre footprint that, in an urban setting, integrates signals from rooftops, impervious surfaces, vegetation patches, and roads. A green roof measurement, by contrast, measures the ET of a specific substrate under controlled conditions. This fundamental scale and surface mismatch limits the achievable correlation, regardless of model quality.

A post-calibration or bias-correction approach, anchored on available field measurements, could partially mitigate this gap. Alternatively, a more precise ET measurement over a spatial footprint more comparable to ECOSTRESS, could provide a more compatible validation and potentially training reference for future model iterations.

4.2. Towards a More Physics-Informed Model

The current model relies exclusively on Sentinel-2 spectral bands and DEM as inputs. While these provide rich structural and vegetative information, they lack direct meteorological forcing. Evapotranspiration is fundamentally driven by atmospheric demand (vapour pressure deficit, solar radiation, wind), which varies independently of vegetation state. Incorporating gridded meteorological variables such as the INCA datasets as auxiliary inputs would create a more

physics-constrained model, potentially improving accuracy during extreme heat events, drought periods, and rapid meteorological transitions.

4.3. Validation Coverage and Generalizability

The present validation is limited to a single urban green roof point. While this provides a valuable benchmark, it cannot characterise model performance across the diversity of land cover types for which the Austria-wide product is used. Future validation campaigns should systematically include:

- Agricultural fields across multiple crop types and growth stages
- Additional urban green infrastructure (parks, street trees, green roofs of varying substrate types)

Such a spatially distributed validation network would allow site-specific bias characterisation, improve confidence in the national product.

5. Conclusion

This work demonstrates a complete pipeline for 10-metre resolution evapotranspiration estimation over Austria, combining Sentinel-2 imagery with spatially-sharpened ECOSTRESS as a training target in a ResNet18 U-Net architecture. The model successfully learns the ECOSTRESS signal and generalises it to unseen Sentinel-2 acquisition dates, as confirmed by strong agreement between model outputs and ECOSTRESS measurements.

Validation against independent ground truth measurements reveals a systematic positive bias partially attributable to the scale mismatch between the 70-metre ECOSTRESS training target and point-scale field measurements.

Future development priorities include the integration of meteorological forcing variables, exploration of a more compatible training reference, and the establishment of a multi-site validation network across Austria's diverse land cover types. The methodology is architecturally transferable to other regions and could be extended to additional ECOSTRESS-derived variables such as land surface temperature and soil moisture.

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